

The Heart of the Land: The Story of Angelim and Cañaverales

MOTHER EARTH MSCA POSTDOCTORAL FELLOWSHIP

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The Heart of the Land: The Story of Angelim and Cañaverales / Alice Lopes Fabris; translated, illustrated, and layout by Alice Lopes Fabris. — 1st ed. — Brussels: VUB & MSCA Mother Earth Project, 2025.

Booklet developed within the framework of the Project Mother Earth (Marie Skłodowska-Curie Actions), funded by the European Union.

DOI: [10.5281/zenodo.18184627](https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.18184627)

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APA

Lopes Fabris, A. (2025). *The heart of the land: The story of Angelim and Cañaverales* (1st ed.). VUB & MSCA Mother Earth Project.

A Note from the Author

This booklet is part of a research project MSCA Mother Earth that aims to understand how the degradation of nature affects the communities that live with it.

In our journey, we visited two very special places: Angelim, in Brazil, and Cañaverales, in Colombia. The people there shared their stories and memories with us.

What you will read here is a adapted version of their histories, told as a story for children, to help everyone understand how people and nature live together, and why it is so important to protect that bond.

We thank the communities of Angelim and Cañaverales for opening their homes and tell us their stories to us.

Long ago, before roads
and cars, families running
from slavery found a
hidden home, a land full
of sparkling rivers, and
forests where they could
live in peace.

A stylized illustration of a landscape. In the foreground, a blue river flows from the bottom left towards the right. The middle ground is a green field. In the background, there is a dark green line of trees. The sky is a bright, pale yellow-green. On the left, a large tree trunk is visible, and its green foliage hangs over the top left corner. On the right, a large tree with a yellow and orange canopy stands prominently. The overall style is painterly and vibrant.

They decided to build their new lives beside one of those rivers, named Angelim.

The image is a pixelated, colorful illustration of a landscape. In the upper portion, three houses with brown roofs and multi-colored walls (yellow, purple, blue) are situated on a green hill. The sky is a light blue with a pattern of darker blue dots. The lower portion of the image shows a bright green field with a dark, winding path or stream. A single, smaller house is visible on the left side of the field, and another house is partially visible on the right edge.

**More and more people
arrived, and, in no time,
houses were build
close to one another.**

**There was always a
friend nearby.**

The people planted cassava, beans, and many other fruits and vegetables. They hunted in the forest, shared what they had, and helped one another in times of need. When planting season came, everyone worked together.

**After the work was done, they
cooked large meals, played music,
and danced until the stars filled the
sky.**

The background is a vibrant, abstract composition. The top half is a textured blue sky with a yellow sun in the top-left corner. The middle section is a bright green field. The bottom section is a purple field with a path of orange and brown brushstrokes winding through it. The text is overlaid on the blue sky and green field.

**The rivers were full of water, and
small streams crossed the paths.
Children ran barefoot through the
fields, laughing as they splashed in
the creeks.**

Life was simple but full of joy.

The people knew how to live with the land, how to listen to the rhythm of the rain, and how to respect the trees that shaded their homes and animals that shared the nature with them.

In the old days, the people also spoke of the enchanted ones, spirits who lived in the waters, the trees, and the wind. These guardians helped the community stay in balance with nature.

One of them is the Mother of the Waters.

She appeared by the river at noon, combing her long hair made of flowing water. The children were taught never to go near the river when she was there. It was not fear, but respect.

**The Mother of the Waters
protected the rivers and the life
around them.**

**And so, the community
lived in harmony.**

**One the years, strangers
arrived with machines and
empty promises.**

They said that if the people sold their land and moved to the city, life would be easier and full of good things. Some believed them and sold their land for little money.

Others were afraid when the machines began to tear the earth and cut the trees.

**Many families left, afraid
or hoping to find a better
life in the city.**

**But the city was not kind: there was
little work, and the people missed
their rivers, their gardens, and the
songs of their home.**

**The machines cleared large areas,
and soon, where there had been
streams and forests, there were now
endless lines of the same trees.**

The eucalyptus grew quickly, but they drank too much water. The rivers began to shrink. The soil cracked in the sun. Without water, the crops no longer grew, and the animals disappeared.

**Then the sugarcane fields
came.**

**The compost was carried
into the river.**

**The fish got sick and died,
and the air smelled bad.**

A landscape painting with a warm, golden-yellow and orange sky. In the background, a dark, forested ridge spans the width of the image. Below the ridge, a valley is filled with green and yellow brushstrokes, suggesting a river valley. In the lower right foreground, a large, dark, textured tree stands prominently. The overall style is expressive and painterly.

**As the years passed,
the community around
the river Angelim grew
smaller and quieter.**

**Only a few families
stayed, remembering the
days of songs, rivers, and
laughter.**

The image features a blue-tinted landscape. On the right side, there is a large, dark silhouette of a tree with dense foliage. At the bottom of the image, there is a dark silhouette of a line of trees or a forest. The background is a bright blue sky with some lighter, wispy clouds. The text is centered in the middle of the image.

Many of the people who once filled the land with music and stories had gone away, as well as the elders who knew the old ways slowly passed on.

A blue-tinted photograph of a tree trunk on the left and a blue sky with clouds in the background. The text is overlaid on the upper right portion of the image.

**Some left before they could
teach the children how to
plant, how to dance, or how
to listen to the river and the
wind.**

**The young ones no longer knew
the Mother of the Waters or the
enchanted ones.**

The life around Angelim was not the same anymore.

The people that stayed often wondered what their lives would be like if their land had been protected; if the communities around Angelim had been allowed to bloom.

**And far away, those who had left
dreamed of coming home again, yet
they understood that hope could only
bloom where their land stood safe
and theirs again.**

**Far away from Angelim,
another community now
faces the same threat:**

**the threat of losing their land and
their home and their community.**

That place is called Cañaverales.

**Cañaverales has a story
much like Angelim's.
About two hundred years
ago, families searching for
freedom and peace found
a beautiful region rich with
water and life.**

There, they built their homes, planted their fields, and created a strong, joyful community where people and nature lived side by side.

**At the heart of the community was a
spring.**

A close-up photograph of a water tap. The tap has a white, circular faucet with a textured, porous appearance. A stream of clear water is flowing from the faucet, creating a white, frothy splash as it hits the surface below. The background is a dark, textured blue. The entire scene is framed by a border of vibrant green leaves, likely from a plant like a lemon tree, which are slightly out of focus.

It is where the water begins its journey, giving life to the people, the animals, and the land itself.

**Many musicians where born
Cañaverales, inspired by the
beauty of the land and the
kindness of its people.**

The elders tell the children about plants, animals, and the old songs that told of their ancestors.

They have a community, memory, and a living connection with the earth that cares for them.

One year, people began
to hear about a coal mine
that would be built nearby.

The mine promised jobs
and progress.

**But the people of Cañaverales
had already seen what
“progress” could do.**

**The coal mine can harm the
spring, the heart that gives life
to the land.**

**Without its water, the fields would
dry, the songs would fade, and life
itself would lose its rhythm.**

**The people know they can not
live on their land without the
spring.**

**They fear the same fate as the people
of Angelim, for both communities
share the same story.**

One lost its forest.

**the other is fighting
to protect its spring.**

**One reminds us of what
happens when the land is stolen.**

the other shows how life
blooms when the land is
protected.

**The story of these two villages
teaches us that the environment is
not just the place where people live;**

**it is part of who they are: their songs,
their food, their traditions, their dreams.**

Protecting the land means protecting their stories, their laughter, and the future of all who depend on it.

**The bond between people and nature
must be protected, so that future
generations can keep the land alive.**

**The story of Angelim and Cañaverales
does not finish here.**

**It remains in the hands of those who still
live there, with their stories, memories
and songs.**

join their journey to protect it.

Funded by
the European Union